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INFLUENCE OF PSYCHO-EMOTIONAL FACTORS ON THE STAGE OF HYPERTENSION DISEASE

Abstract.

The article examines the impact of psychogenic factors on the stage of hypertension, and also analyzes various risk factors, including genetic heredity, age, gender, physical inactivity, obesity, smoking, alcohol abuse, and psychoemotional disorders. The author presents the results of a survey of patients with hypertension who were treated in the Chernivtsi cardiology dispensary. The survey was conducted using standardized questionnaires, which made it possible to characterize in detail the influence of depression, anxiety, hypochondria and other psychogenic factors on the occurrence and stage of hypertension.

The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) and the Hamilton scale were used to determine the presence of anxiety and depressive disorders. The Zung Self-Rating Depression Scale was used for self-diagnosis of depression, the interpretation of which was carried out using a specially developed unified and structured clinical interview. This made it possible to distinguish four levels of depressive states and to identify the most significant factors of depressive disorders, such as a constant decrease in mood, feelings of guilt, suicidal thoughts and the desire to die, reduced work capacity, insomnia, anxiety of somatic and mental origin, reluctance to physical activity and various sexual disorders.

The paper also analyzed the severity of depression among men and women depending on the degree of hypertension, and reliably proved the relationship between mental factors and the course of hypertension using the χ^2 method. The analysis using χ^2 showed the reliability of the negative influence of the combined risk factors of hypertension ($P < 0.05$). Based on the results of the research, the most influential risk factors were determined: smoking, low physical activity, constant alcohol consumption and various depressive disorders.

Keywords: *hypertension, psycho-emotional disorders, anxiety, depression, psycho-emotional states, psycho-traumatic situations, risk factors.*

Introduction. High blood pressure (BP) is a serious medical problem. According to the World Health Organization, one in four men and one in five women suffer from hypertension, which is more than a billion people in the world. The development of a system of individual correction of disorders associated with stress caused by military events is extremely important in the context of mental health problems and psychosocial consequences of crisis-traumatic situations [1].

The consequences of psychotraumatic situations always arise gradually. At the present moment, the population of Ukraine is under the influence of constant psycho-traumatic factors. War is the main reason for the development of post-traumatic stress disorders, acute stress reactions and military mental injuries. Chronic stress is an independent predictor of both cardiovascular disease and depression. [5].

Presenting main material. Health problems in wartime conditions are associated with the instability of the socio-political situation in the country, which led to the deterioration of the mental health of the population and an increase in cardiovascular risk in a large part of the population (military, as well as victims of hostilities and related social upheavals) due to experienced traumatic stress [2].

Permanent psychotraumatic situations lead to the strengthening of negative psycho-emotional states and significant behavioral changes of people. In Ukraine, the problem of psycho-emotional disorders is relevant

at the global level. Unstable economic and political conditions in the country caused exacerbation of hypertension under the influence of anxiety-depressive and emotional factors. According to the results of recent scientific research, it has been proven that the leading psychosocial risk factors for hypertension are anxiety, depression and various psycho-emotional disorders. It was found that psychoemotional disorders and hypertension have the same physiological and pathogenetic mechanisms (dysfunction of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal systems).

Chronic stress is an independent predictor of both cardiovascular disease and depression. As a result of this dysregulation and the effect of stress, the activation of the sympathetic nervous system develops, which affects the occurrence and progression of hypertension [3].

Thus, as of July 15, 2022, more than 6.1 million Ukrainians emigrated abroad, and more than 6.2 million became internally displaced persons within the country [4]. This led to the emergence of a mass psycho-traumatic situation with prolonged consequences.

Chronic depression increases the length of stay of patients in cardiology departments, negatively affects work capacity, leads to disability and is a cause of coronary death. In addition, depression affects the onset and course of hypertension through behavioral mechanisms. For example, refusing to take medication or abusing it. The occurrence and course of

hypertensive diseases depend on the lifestyle (disordered sleep and rest). The problem of cardiovascular diseases that arose as a result of psycho-emotional disorders is one of the important problems in medicine. Prolonged psycho-emotional disorders are the basis for the occurrence of cardiovascular diseases, especially hypertension.

In addition, literature data confirmed that the combined effect of various psycho-emotional risk factors leads to the occurrence of hypertension.

The purpose of the article: to analyze the impact of psycho-emotional disorders on the occurrence and complications of the course of hypertension.

Materials and methods:

To diagnose depression, we conducted a study that included 130 patients of the Chernivtsi Regional Cardiology Dispensary (70 men and 65 women) who were undergoing inpatient treatment at the Chernivtsi Cardiology Dispensary during 2021-2023. Depending on the degree of hypertension, all patients were divided into 3 groups. 1st degree - a mild form of hypertension (20 men and 15 women); 2nd stage - moderate form (40 men and 35 women); 3 degree severe form of hypertension (10 men and 10 women). The average age of the examined patients was 54.5 years. The presence of anxiety and depressive disorders was determined using the hospital anxiety and depression scale. The Zung Self-Rating Depression Scale was used in our study for self-diagnosis of depression. Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS); Hamilton scale. The Chi-square method of statistical analysis was used in the statistical processing of the material.

The Zang scale has proven its effectiveness in conducting various studies on the screening assessment of depressive disorders, is endowed with high

sensitivity and specificity, and does not require large economic costs. Thanks to clearly formulated 20 questions (10 positive and 10 negative), patients independently identify 4 levels of depressive states (absence of depression, mild, moderate and severe form of depressive disorders). To interpret this scale, we developed a special unified and structured clinical interview, which consisted of 15 items and took about 25 minutes. Points were assessed according to the following gradation:

- 0-7 — absence of depressive disorders (8 men and 5 women);
- 8-13 — mild depressive disorders (12 men and 10 women);
- 14-18 — depressive disorders of medium severity (30 men and 25 women)
- 19 and over—severe depressive disorders (8 men and 7 women).

The most significant factors of depressive disorders were used in the study: constant lowering of mood, feelings of guilt, suicidal statements and desire for one's own death, reduced work capacity, insomnia, anxiety of somatic and mental origin, reluctance to physical activity, various sexual disorders. All points were summed up.

To determine the severity of the manifestations of anxiety and depression in our work, the modernized and unified HADS scale was used, in which each answer contains a clear interpretation (often, constantly, sometimes, never). The obtained results were divided into 4 groups (absence of psycho-emotional disorders, mild depression, depressive disorders of moderate severity and severe depressive disorders).

Table No. 1.

The degree of expressiveness of depression among men and women depending on the degree of hypertension

No	Degree of expressiveness depression	Degree of hypertension											
		1 degree (soft form)				2 degrees (moderate form)				3 degree (severe form)			
		males		females		males		females		males		females	
abs.	%	abs.	%	abs.	%	abs.	%	abs.	%	abs.	%		
1	Stable psycho-emotional state	10	50	4	26.7	3	7.5	3	8.57	-	-	-	-
2	Insignificant depression	6	30	6	40	15	37.5	13	37.1	2	20	2	20
3	Average level depressed disorders	4	20	5	33.3	18	45	16	45.7	3	30	4	40
4	Severe level depressed disorders	-	-	-	-	4	10	3	8.57	5	50	4	40
	In total	20	100	15	100	40	100	35	100	10	100	10	100

It can be seen from the table that a stable psycho-emotional state is more common with 1 degree of hypertension (50% among men and 26.7% among women). With a severe form of hypertension, there is no stable psycho-emotional state, both among men and among women. The average level of depressive disorders is more common in hypertensive disease of the 2nd degree (45% of men and 45.7% of women). A severe level of depressive disorders is most common in

3rd degree hypertension (50% of men and 40% of women).

In the presence of hypertension of the 1st degree, it is accompanied by leading symptoms of anxiety. Hypertensive disease of the 2nd degree is accompanied by frequent depressive and hypochondriac disorders with the presence of asthenia. Hypertensive disease of the 3rd degree is characterized by significantly pronounced depressive and hypochondriac symptoms compared to anxiety symptoms.

Table No 2.

The relationship between mental risk factors and the occurrence and course of hypertension

No	Mental factors	χ^2 (χ -square)	R (significance level)
1.	Anxiety	1.78	P>0.05
2.	Asthenia	1.72	P>0.05
3.	Hypochondria	3.12	P>0.05
4.	Depression	1.96	P>0.05
5.	Emotional disorders	1.83	P>0.05

The assessment of the overall influence of χ^2 was carried out using statistical tables, taking into account the number of degrees of freedom (table No. 2). The analysis using χ^2 showed the reliability of the negative influence of the combined risk factors of hypertension (P<0.05). For example, anxiety, depression and hypodynamia (more than 30%). This indicates a potentiated effect in the combined action of these factors, i.e. strengthening the influence of some factors by others.

According to the results of our research, the most influential risk factors were identified: cigarette smoking - 50% (35% of men and 15% of women), low physical activity - 30%, constant alcohol consumption (7% of men and 4% of women), various depressive disorders - 65%.

Conclusion. Among the risk factors for the course of hypertension, anxiety and depression disorders have a leading influence. With a severe form of hypertension, there is no stable psycho-emotional state, both among men and among women. A severe level of depressive disorders is most common in 3rd degree hypertension (50% of men and 40% of women).

In addition, the course of hypertensive disease is complicated by the presence of hypodynamia - 43%, obesity - 10%, cigarette smoking - 50% (35% of men and 15% of women), low physical activity - 30%, constant alcohol consumption - (7%, men and 4% of women). Using the χ^2 method, a combination of depressive and various risk factors for hypertensive disease was revealed, and it was reliably proven (P>0.05) that anxious and depressive states reinforce each other and are interconnected.

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